

3-OXIMINOMETHYLSALICYLIC ACID AS AN ANALYTICAL REAGENT.
PART II. SPECTROPHOTOMETRIC DETERMINATION
OF URANIUM

BY ASIT KUMAR RAY AND PRIYADARANJAN RÂY*

The use of 3-oximinomethylsalicylic acid as a reagent for the spectrophotometric determination of uranium (VI), with which it develops an orange-red colour in alkaline solution, is described. The wave-length of 400 m μ is found most suitable for absorption measurement. The optimum pH of the solution lies between 6.70 and 9.30 with an excess of the reagent, at least 5 to 6 times the molar proportion of uranium, for the maximum development of colour. The colour is stable at room temperature below 30°. Beer's law holds good in the concentration range of 7.14–119.0 p.p.m. uranium. Sensitivity is 0.12 γ U/c.c. The composition (1:1) of the coloured species has been evaluated by Job's method and the probable constitution suggested. Most cations and anions interfere with the determination of uranium. Hence a preliminary separation of 'uranium' from the interfering ions is essential.

The colorimetric methods for uranium are not so sensitive as those of many other elements. Recently Yoe *et al.* (*Anal. Chem.*, 1953, 25, 1200) have proposed dibenzoylmethane, C₆H₅CO.CH₂.COC₆H₅, as the most sensitive colorimetric reagent for uranium. But the insolubility of the reagent in water is a great disadvantage. Of the various other organic reagents that are in use for the colorimetric determination of uranium, mention may be made of salicylic acid (Müller, *Chem. Ztg.*, 1919, 43, 739), salicylamide (Rây *et al.*, this *Journal*, 1953, 30, 491) and salicylhydroxamic acid (Bhaduri, *Z. anal. Chem.*, 1957, 154, 103).

3-Oximinomethylsalicylic acid (Ray and Rây, this *issue*, p. 133) reacts with uranium(VI) to develop an orange-red colour in alkaline solution. The colour is fairly intense and is quite stable. It was therefore considered suitable for use as a colorimetric reagent for uranium. The optimum wave-length chosen for measurement of the colour intensity is 400 m μ , where the freshly prepared reagent solution has no absorption. An alkaline solution of the reagent on heating, however, shows some absorption in this region. The colour intensity of a solution containing uranium (VI) and an excess of 3-oximinomethylsalicylic acid reaches its maximum value at pH 7.0 and remains constant up to pH 9.30. A further increase in pH, however, leads to a considerable fading of the colour. The colour intensity increases rapidly with an increase in the proportion of the reagent up to 5 to 6 times the molar proportion of

*Present address : 50/1, Hindusthan Park, Calcutta-29.

uraniuim and then remains constant. Beer's law holds good over the range of 7.14 to 119 p.p.m. of uranium. Sensitivity (0.12 γ U/c.c.) is the same as that for salicylamidoxime (Bandyopadhyay, *ibid.*, 1956, 33, 269).

A study of the coloured complex in solution by Job's method of continued variation, as modified by Vosburgh and Cooper (*J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1941, 63, 437; 1942, 64, 1630), shows that its composition is given by 1:1 metal-ligand ratio as in the case of salicylamidoxime. Since the coloured species is insoluble in organic solvents like ether, chloroform, ethyl acetate, etc., but is highly soluble in water, it may reasonably be concluded that it is an ionic complex, possibly of the anionic type, as it is formed in an alkaline region. In fact, salicylamidoxime, which is known to form 1:2 complexes with many bivalent metals at relatively low pH regions, also affords 1:1 complexes at higher pH values owing to both the phenolic (-OH) and oximino (=NOH) groups being involved in salt formation.

Many common anions and cations have been found to interfere with the colour formation, excepting a few like NO_3^- , Cl^- , and SO_4^{2-} , which do not interfere even at relatively very high concentrations. Anions like phosphate, borate, oxalate, citrate, tartrate, fluoride, etc. interfere even when present in small amounts. A previous separation of uranium from the interfering ions is therefore necessary.

EXPERIMENTAL

A Unicam SP 600 spectrophotometer was used for the measurement of absorption of solutions, using cells of suitable thickness in order to have the transmittancy values within the proper range (20 to 80%) for minimum error. Measurements of pH were carried out with the help of a Cambridge pH-meter (Bench pattern) using glass electrode (for 0.9 pH) or alkali-glass electrode (for pH 9 and above) and a saturated calomel reference electrode.

A freshly prepared aqueous solution of 3-oximinomethylsalicylic acid was always used for the experiments. A solution of uranyl nitrate was prepared by dissolving 5 g. of $\text{UO}_2(\text{NO}_3)_2 \cdot 6\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (A. R.) in 500 c.c. of water containing some free nitric acid (G. R.). This was standardised by precipitation with CO_2 -free ammonia gas and then igniting the precipitate to U_3O_8 . From this stock solution others of desired strengths were prepared by requisite dilution.

Stock solutions (0.1M and 0.5M) were prepared from G.R. quality KOH, and these were used for the adjustment of pH of the solutions. Solutions of diverse ions were prepared from suitable salts (reagent grade) and were standardised as usual.

Optimum Wave-length for the Absorption Measurements.—The optical densities of a number of 0.0005M uranyl nitrate solutions in the presence of a large excess of 3-oximinomethylsalicylic acid at pH 8.78 were measured. The absorption of a pure reagent solution of the same concentration as in the coloured solution (0.005M) was

also measured at pH 8 to 9, at various wave-lengths for comparison. The results are represented by Fig. 1.

FIG. 1

A : 0.0035 M. $UO_2(NO_3)_2$ and 0.005 M-reagent ; pH 8.76.
 B : 0.005 M-Reagent ; pH 8.72.

From Fig. 1 it is evident that 400 mμ is the optimum wave-length for measurement, since at this wave-length the uranyl-3-oximinomethylsalicylic acid colour shows strong absorption while the reagent has got practically no absorption.

FIG. 2

UO^{2+} -3-oximinomethylsalicylic acid.

A : Effect of pH.

B : Effect of the reagent.

The optical density of the reagent (0.005M) remains unchanged between 2.8 and 9.36 pH.

Effect of pH on the Colour Intensity.—The effect of pH on the colour intensity is shown in Fig 2, curve A, from which it is evident that the colour intensity reaches its maximum value at pH 6.70 and thereafter remains unchanged up to pH 9.38.

Influence of the Reagent Concentration on the Colour Intensity.—It is observed that at least an excess of the reagent over 5 to 6 times the molar proportion of uranium is necessary for the development of colour (cf. Fig. 2, curve B).

Beer's Law.—The system obeys Beer's law in the range of concentration from 7.14 to 119.0 p.p.m. uranium (cf. Fig. 3).

FIG. 3
Beer's law.

UO_2^{2+} -reagent colour at pH 8.6 ± 0.2 .

Stability of the Colour at Room Temperature.—The colour is stable at room temperature. With the rise of temperature the colour intensity was found to decrease appreciably over 30° as shown below.

TABLE I

$\text{UO}_2^{2+} = 0.00025M$. pH = 8.38. Reagent = 0.0025M.						
Temp.	...	25°	30°	35°	40°	45°
O.D. (400 mμ)	...	0.532	0.510	0.502	0.481	0.471
Sensitivity : 0.12 γU/c.c. (Sandell).						

Composition of the Coloured Product.—The composition was determined by the method of continued variation. In order to prevent the precipitation of uranium from solutions containing smaller amounts of 3-oximinomethylsalicylic acid (R), it was found necessary to work with very dilute solutions. At this extremely low concentrations the absorption of the free UO_2^{2+} ions was found to be negligible at the wave-lengths (400 mμ and 420 mμ) employed for the measurement of the colour intensity, while the reagent did not show any absorption at these wave-lengths. The

results are represented in Fig. 4. The maximum absorption is shown by a solution of composition 1 metal : 1 ligand.

FIG. 4

Job's method
 UO_2^{2+} : 3-Oximinomethyl Salicylic Acid
 pH 8.6 $\pm$ 0.2

Influence of Foreign Ions on the Uranyl-3-oximinomethylsalicylic Acid Colour.—The effect of diverse ions was studied as usual and the approximate tolerance limits were determined. The latter denote the maximum permissible concentration of the foreign ion in the solution under investigation which affect the optical density by less than $\pm 2\%$. Most of the common cations and anions were found to interfere, but NO_3^- , Cl^- and SO_4^{2-} had no effect, even when they occurred in 200, 100, 400 times the amount of uranium present respectively.

Estimation of Uranium.—From a consideration of the experimental results, recorded here, the following procedure for the estimation of uranium by 3-oximinomethylsalicylic acid may be recommended.

For the determination of uranium in commercial materials, ores, minerals, etc., a solution of the sample should be prepared and all interfering ions present should be removed by standard procedures. The pure uranium solution as chloride or nitrate is then used for the estimation. An aliquot is to be treated with more than seven times the molar proportion of a freshly prepared solution of 3-oximinomethylsalicylic acid and diluted to a known volume with water, adjusting the pH of the solution to 7.5–9.2 by adding alkali (KOH). The uranium content of the final solution should remain between 14 and 115 p.p.m. The optical density of the solution is measured at 400 mμ in a cell of suitable thickness to have the transmission 80–20%, against a reagent blank. From the optical density value, the concentration of uranium can be calculated, knowing the extinction coefficient.